

Mathematik, Naturwissenschaften, Wirtschaft & Informatik (/fb4/)

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Workshop: Research Data Management, ISMLL, why and how?

Dienstag, 12. November 2019 um 18:00 Uhr

Learn more about Research Data Management

Where? Samelsoncampus, Room B026, (Samelsonplatz 1, 31141 Hildesheim)

When? 06:00 p.m. - 08:00 p.m.

Presenter: Annette Strauch, M.A

Oberseminar: Forschungsdatenmanagement - Research Data Management, ISMLL.

Information: Research Data Management is an integral part of "good scientific practice". This workshop intends to inform about data management planning, options for data publication and services for data storage and file organization at Hildesheim University Foundation.

Do you have research data at ISMLL? Everyone has! Then come and learn about Research Data Management to deal with all of your data for future happiness. In the workshop, the most important aspects of RDM will be considered:

- research data life cycle
- research data policies
- data management plan
- structuring of data
- documentation
- storage and backup
- long-term archiving
- access security
- publication of research data
- re-use of research data
- legal aspects.

Workshop participants will be able to:

- recognise the importance of good practice in managing research data and apply it within their own work context
- apply knowledge gained to be able to draw up a data management plan and maintain it throughout the project life (the RDMO tool will be explained)

Participants

The workshop is intended for the Oberseminar participants (ISMLL, <https://www.ismll.uni-hildesheim.de/> (<https://www.ismll.uni-hildesheim.de/>)) including all students and researchers.